

Workflow Description of UTOPIA- μ GA system

Figure 1. Directory structure of the UTOPIA- μ GA system, including `ga.inp`, `mga_utoxia.exe`, the `exp` directory, and the `Template` directory. When the optimization system starts, the contents of the `Template` directory are automatically copied into `Run1`—`Run5` to initialize five populations.

Important Files

Ga.inp: A namelist file for the genetic algorithm (GA). It specifies GA options such as population size, number of parameters, the crossover option, and parameter ranges.

Mga_utoxia.exe: The executable file of the UTOPIA- μ GA system.

Template Directory: Contains template scripts for running UTOPIA- μ GA. When the optimization system runs:

- It requires `ga.restart` to restart and continue the GA process.
- It generates scripts to control UTOPIA runs (`run_utoxia.sh`, `wait_utoxia.sh`)
- It generates plotting scripts for evaluating the fitness function for representative soil layers (`makeftn *.sh`)
- It automatically copies the templates into the `Run1`—`Run5` directories to initialize five populations when the optimization system starts.